

DELIVERABLE

2023-DL.4.1.1 REVIEW OF EXISTING TRAINING COURSES FOR THE TURKEY WELFARE ON FARM ASSESSMENT

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1. Introduction

The European reference Centre for Animal Welfare for Poultry and other Small Farmed Animals (EURCAW-Poultry-SFA) aims to review and assess the existing training courses and materials for turkey welfare assessment on farm in use at Member States (MS) or at other levels (*e.g.*, regional training courses). The report includes a description of existing courses and materials considering information on objectives, content and training materials as well as an identification of the gaps that the Centre might address in the future.

2. Methodology used

The EURCAW-Poultry-SFA requested from the Competent Authority contact points at the beginning of 2023 the National training materials (from 2010 to 2022) for assessment of turkey welfare on-farm. The Centre only received replies from ten MSs. Most of them did not organize any national training for this topic. We only received material from two training courses (see Annex 1 for more information about them):

Table 1. General information about the National training courses revised related to turkey welfare on-farm.

Title/topic	Year	Num. of editions	Location
Turkeys	2009	1	Portugal
Turkey welfare	2010	1	Italy

These lectures were reviewed in order to score at which extend the indicators for the assessment of the requirements of the legislation were covered. The welfare indicators were retrieved from those identified in the deliverable *2022-DL 2.1.4 - List of welfare indicators to assess turkeys' welfare on-farm* (available online [here](#)). However, while all the ABIs were included, only those RBIs and MBIs that need for training were considered. For this purpose, each indicator was scored according to the coverage level found in the training material as follows:

0 = indicator considered to be “not covered” as there is no evidence to be mentioned in any lecture of the training material reviewed.

1 = indicator considered to be “partially covered” as it was mentioned in training material but without evidence of detailed description of the methodology (*i.e.*, found in text).

2 = indicator considered to be “well covered” as it was mentioned in the training material and with evidence of detailed description of the methodology and assessment (*i.e.*, found in text along with audio-visual support such as photography or videos, or case studies).

3. Assessment of the training material

Lectures from nation training courses were analysed and the coverage of the welfare indicators were scored. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.1. Coverage scores of the selected Animal (ABI) and Resource-based Indicators (RBI) for the assessment of welfare of turkeys on farm and at slaughterhouse (SH) from the revised National training material.

Indicator	Type of indicator	Farm/SH	Training material, year	Coverage score
Undersized turkeys (runts)	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Dirtiness of the animals	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Panting, huddling or shivering	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Loss of feather	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Stocking density	RBI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	2 1
Light intensity and lighting programme	RBI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	1 0
Temperature and Humidity measurements	RBI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Noxious gases concentration	RBI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Dustiness	RBI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Litter quality	RBI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 1
Skin lesions (footpad dermatitis and hock burns)	ABI	Farm/SH	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 2
Head wounds	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Back wounds	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	1 1
Tail wounds	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Immobility	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Lameness	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 1
Sick turkeys	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Terminally ill turkeys	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 0
Dead turkeys	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX Italy, 2010	0 1
Aggressiveness	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX	0

			Italy, 2010	0
Expression of positive behaviours	ABI	Farm	Portugal, XXXX	0
			Italy, 2010	0

4. Gaps of knowledge

Lectures analysed from the national training courses were short and addressed general welfare aspects of the turkey production, but few indicators were described. Only one RBI (stocking density) was apparently well described in one of the lectures, and only one ABI (footpad dermatitis) was apparently well described in the other lecture. However, at glance there is not enough evidence to affirm that the methodology for their assessment is fully covered.

Therefore, there is a lack of training material and description for most of the indicators (either ABIs or RBIs) that the Centre identified in deliverable *2022-DL 2.1.4*. This report identifies the different indicators that could be used to assess legal requirements for turkey production, along with their methods for assessment, and their feasibility and reliability. Iceberg indicators are also highlighted. The list is not exhaustive, but EURCAW-Poultry-SFA chose the most relevant ones according to their knowledge and the available scientific data. This document could be used as a basis for a future training course specifically addressed to official inspectors regarding the assessment of turkey welfare during inspections.

The Centre has also been working in dissemination material to assess indicators and to show best practices from turkey production, which can be found here:

- Factsheet: Environmental enrichment and winter garden in a turkey barn (available online [here](#))
- Factsheet: Injurious pecking in turkeys (available online [here](#))

These factsheets can be used as complementary material for any training course about on-farm turkey welfare.

5. Conclusions

- 1) Training courses on turkey welfare on farm for official inspectors are really scarce.
- 2) The training courses that were analyzed lack a lot of information about indicators and methods to be used to assess turkey welfare.
- 3) EURCAW-Poultry-SFA has produced a document about welfare indicators and methods of assessment for turkey on-farm (available on-line). This document could be used as a basis for future training courses specifically addressed to official inspectors regarding assessment of turkey welfare during inspections.

ANNEX 1: National training material

Country	Portugal
Year	2009 (presented several times since)
Title	<i>Perus.</i> Turkeys.
Duration	Not specified
Objective	Not specified.
Content	1 lecture about turkey welfare on farm and legislation.

Country	Italy
Year	2010
Title	<i>Benessere del tacchino.</i> Turkey welfare.
Duration	Not specified.
Objective	Not specified.
Content	1 lecture about turkey welfare on-farm, included in a training course about welfare of farmed animals (<i>Corso di formazione sul benessere degli animali da reddito in allevamento – D.Lgs 146/2001</i>)